

Gender Inclusiveness in the Digitalization of the Nigerian Economy

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Abstract

Gender, especially in developing countries are experiencing poor participation and inclusion in the digital and economic activities in the nation Nigeria. Sustaining the economy through digitalization in a multiple inequalities between male and their female counterpart calls for apt attention than the cursory approach in the economic structures of the nation. Thus, the study is to exhaustively review the significance of gender (women) inclusiveness in the digitalization of Nigeria economy, challenges, prospects in promoting gender equalities and empowerment of the women. The qualitative research approach is adopted in this study with review of scholars' expressions on gender inclusiveness in economy activities of a nation. The study reveals low percentage of women in socio-economic digital development, information communication technology activities and policy drafting /development via digitalization. Base on the results, the study recommends deliberate information communication technology policy that will attract, encourage and enhance activities gender participation in the development of the Nigerian economy via digitalization.

Keywords: Gender, Inclusivity, Digitalization, Economy

Introduction

In some developing countries in the world women are scarcely at the forefront of innovations and creativities in the economy activities due to the constant gender exclusiveness perspective of that country. As observed by Okiyi Esowo on reasons for the exclusiveness of women ranges on: lack of access to internet resources in most communities in a nation, sex discrimination in some career jobs, technical education and some engineering, science jobs etc. These career areas that women are exclusive, created gender gap in the labour market leading to challenges in the global market economy. The identified career jobs, have witnessed tremendous communication technology (ICT) in its operations. Women according to the United Nation Organisation survey, make up half of the world's population.² Yet, thirty seven percent of these women, do not have access to the information communication technology (internet) as to actively participate in the digitalization process of the nation's economy. Low participation and inclusiveness of women in the digitalization of the economy becomes abnormal trends in most developing nation's economy.

It becomes the thrust in this study to explore the inclusiveness of gender in the digitalization of the nation's economy. Formidable gender inclusiveness in the digital operations has the propensity of spurring greater participation of women in the creative and innovative sector of economy of most countries with the desired results. In addition to this, the challenges women face in accessing the technological knowledge, skills, internet resources and the support needed to thrive and be celebrated as inventors, creators of contents; entrepreneurs etc. are to be critically examined. This, it is hoped to bring to fore the creativity of women in the economy. As well unravel communal tangles on women involvements in economy activities, strategies to help improve women participation and their knowledge in economy development of a nation. With gender inclusiveness in the economic activities, the work force is boosted. Adequate knowledge on usage of the digital system in the growth of the economy is attained which in turn limit paucity of knowledge on the procedure required on the use of digital system in economic development.

Conceptualization of Gender Inclusiveness and Digitalization

Gender inclusiveness as remarked by Anita G. entails “increased number of male and female innovative and creative ideas in leadership positions in the economy drive of a nation.”³ She expanded this expression by stating the gains in engaging women to utilize their potentials as entrepreneurs, creators and innovators in fostering economic growth of nations. What this implies is that gender inclusiveness enhances successive, innovation, creativity and inventions that plays tremendous role in promoting business interest, entrepreneurship and promotion of intellectual property rights in economic activities.⁴ Kwame suggests fostering of a balance in a world where creativity and innovation thrives in the economy.⁵ The concept speaks on creating a platform and opportunities for women with viable ideas to create a profitable niche with their male counterparts in economy space of a nation.

For Dzidonu, gender inclusiveness fosters research and development that aide in bringing new ideas to the market / economy.⁶ In a situation where there is inclusiveness, both sex will have necessary funds and comparative advantage which makes it easier for than to maximize their potentials as innovators and creators in modern economy society operations. Their economic rights and opportunities, gender budgeting as part of programme support to the government economy activities, fiscal responsibility legislation of the nation with strategies for main streaming gender into all section of budget becomes a standard for public financial management towards good governance.

Interestingly, gender inclusiveness eliminate disparity which is a key in the aspect of economic activities of a nation.⁷ Nations of the world including Nigeria has its own stage of economic growth. As such, the nations have to move at a pace that fosters development. This entails gender budgeting which ensures incorporation of both sex needs into fiscal policies that promotes government accountability in the fiscal policy in short and long economy policies that will lower gender gap.

On conceptualization of digitalization, human globally are experiencing an extra ordinary transitioning in technology. The increased technology adoptions by human have helped many people in their daily lives. For some groups, digital disparity still remains and this is attributed to their lack of technical skill and. Thus, it becomes imperative to conceptualize digitalization in the growth of economy of a nation. As remarked by Ronnic Downes, digitalization implies “the use of internet for religious, social, political and economic activities.”⁸ He averred that factor(s) that facilitated the use of the internet is based on needs of a targeted group. The statistical analyses made on the needs from the ITU World Telecommunication / Information Communication Technology indicators database suggesting that more men than women uses the internet globally.

The statistical figure indicates that 37% of all women are on line compared with the 41% of all men on line globally. Men on line compared with the 41% of all men on line globally. It suggest that 1.3 billion of women and 1.5 billion men uses or have access to internet. For the developing nations which Nigeria is included, the statistics shows 475 million female internet users. While 483 million male internet are on line. The gender gap in the developing world stands at 16% fewer women that uses the internet compare to 2% fewer women than men in the developed world.⁹

Osubor V.I. and Konyeha S, conceptualized digitalization as a “process individual and group having accessing to information communication technology (ICT) to increase self-esteem reduce isolation, access to markets, economic empowerment and growth, health care etc.”¹⁰. The process builds capacity and cultural transformation, socio-economic and organizational community structures that can enable the genders lead and collectivity empowerment of their sex especially the female gender.¹¹ In other words, gender inclusiveness on digital process enhances increase in productivity, promote sustainable growth, peace and better health care delivery and in turn fosters economic development.

However, the conceptualization of gender inclusiveness and digitalization process finds its expression in Nigeria where there is a clear gender disparity in the digital field. Many women lack access to learning and training opportunities to help them take up work in technology-related fields. This means that many women are disadvantaged as regards employment opportunities in the various fields of careers. Our digital inclusion

programs provide these opportunities for young women and girls to enable them to become productive members of their communities and leverage on technology. However, achieving the economic development will be impossible without supporting a gender-parity future in our nation's digital property system in the growth of the economy. This is as important as the subject of equal pay for equal work, equal legal recognition, and the opportunity for top leadership in all spheres of society.

Interestingly, Michael Sylvia states that women and girls are no longer mere consumers of technologies, innovations or inventions¹². They are now becoming top creators, founders, pioneers, entrepreneurs, designers, and artists in different sectors including education, healthcare, hospitality, finance, logistics, entertainment, and social impacts. This presents a promising future for increased female participation in the innovation and creativity landscape in Nigeria digital economic growth. It is noteworthy that expanding access to the protection of women's ingenuity is vital for women's empowerment and the inherent benefits to Nigeria in terms of reduction in the poverty rate and child malnutrition, better mental health outcomes.¹³

The need to address the foundational issues on girl-child education, healthcare, and digital inclusion cannot be overemphasis. Access to high-quality education for all girls in Nigeria and around the world remains a non-negotiable factor for achieving gender parity in the digitalization of the economy. Unsurprisingly, educated women are more likely to interact in the formal economy characterized by skilled labour participation, business formalization, and better recognition in the digital growth of the nation's economic.¹⁴ Therefore, gender inclusiveness in the digital growth of the economic offers opportunities for vulnerable girls from poor families and under-resourced communities across the states to be serious about closing the gender gap in innovation and creativity in Nigeria economy.

Challenges of Gender Inclusivity in the Digitalization growth of Nigerian Economy

An analysis of the key challenges to the utilization of ICT to promote socio-economic development, and in particular, the achievement in poverty alleviation, health, education, gender equality, and environmental sustainability illustrate the possible impacts of ICT as an enabling tool for socioeconomic development that directly or indirectly impact on the achievements of the gender inclusiveness one of the challenges is the technical and sociocultural barriers exacerbate women's exclusion from the benefits of ICT for economic development. Inaccessibility to ICT has widened educational, healthcare, information and communication gaps between urban and remote communities genders.¹⁵

In addition to the identified challenges, Anita identified location, lack of infrastructure and connectivity, time and money, lack of relevant content, low education and literacy, social norms and perceptions as women most significant barriers to the utilization of ICT for economic growth development. The systematic documentation of information and communication needs of women in the global assert that obstacle to ICT accessibility and utilization are generally structural (time, location, and illiteracy) and not personal (for example, a prohibition from a relative).¹⁶ These challenges as Kwame D.D assert greatly account for the reasons why Nigerian women are often underrepresented in terms of ICT access and utilization, despite the great emphasis placed on the use of ICT in Nigeria economic activities.¹⁷

Strategies of Enhancing Women Participation in Digitalization of the Economy of Nigeria

Identified below are suggested strategies of ensuring active women participation in the digitalization of the Nigerian economy:

- Supporting Women in their quest for Inclusiveness in the Digitalization of the Economy
Women from different walks of life and backgrounds should be educated on the importance of digital economy, shown how digitalized economy work, and supported to monetize their products for economic gains. For example, the recent Women IT Training Program initiated by the Nigerian Breweries is a welcome development. The programmes provides generous support for fresh male/ female graduates across Nigeria to acquire meaningful work experience, enhance their skills, and learn from leading professionals.¹⁸

Nancy J.H and Sophia H. speaks on intellectual property such as copyright, trademark, and patents that gives women legal protection for their creative or innovative works that solve real societal challenges. Intellectual property has been identified as the original creations of the human mind and intellect worthy of exclusive rights to encourage more creations that make life better for others. For example, the super talented Nigerian artist, Temilade Openiyi, better known as Tems won her first Grammy Award in the 2023 'Best Melodic Rap Performance' category for her distinctive vocal contribution to the hit song 'Wait For U' by Future featuring Drake and herself. She is now an inspiration to millions of women and girls in Africa. This achievement can be protected and marketed when women understand fully how to utilized ICT facilities in marketing their products and services.

- **Bringing Intellectual Property to the Grassroots**

It should be noted that women are not a homogenous group. While there are similarities in needs and challenges among females, there are differences in terms of educational attainment, language, income status, geographical location, age group, and cultural background. In the words of Ifeoluwa Olubiyi, “Enlightenment of women in intellectual property matter is also important since many of them work in informal sectors and in small and medium entrepreneurship scheme (SMES) but do not know about how to create their Intellectual property rights.” In addition, encouraging female participation in the intellectual property system requires a large-scale formalization and digitalization drive for women's businesses by integrating professional support including free legal assistance through local trade associations or groups. This can be done by mainstreaming intellectual property literacy among non-English speaking men/women and them using their mother tongue. Achieving this will require engaging intellectual property educators and practitioners who are not only fluent in local languages but culturally competent when working with females.²⁰

Contrary to some opinions, women not having ICT background can equally participate in innovation and creative economy through the use of digital facilities. For example, local women/men selling *Àkàrà* (fried beans cake) at various bus stops across the country can be organized, trained, mentored, and financed to improve the quality of their *Àkàrà*, while providing support for branding, scalability, and the appropriate intellectual property application (e.g., trademark and trade secrets).

Ending Female Digital Poverty

Women and girls, especially in developing countries are experiencing digital poverty the inability to access high-quality digital devices, low-tech skills, limited internet usage, and poor connectivity. For anyone, digital poverty equals loss of productivity and socioeconomic opportunities resulting in social, financial, and economic exclusion.²¹ While there is progress in digital inclusion and ubiquitous internet penetration in Nigeria, there are multiple inequalities between urban and rural men/women. For example, the men/women selling vegetables in one of the most remote areas in Ahoada, Rivers State may be uncomfortable using their 2G phones for making transfers due to the cash scarcity that affected many Nigerians in 2023. They may even be at a loss having to receive a 500 naira credit alert for their goods after bank charges. Moreover, those in the urban centres enjoy better internet services than rural dwellers. Except a concerted effort exists to end widespread digital poverty disproportionately affecting women and girls, we may not achieve gender parity in intellectual property as the key to Nigeria's sustainable development and competitiveness.²² Iyere noted that creativity and innovation are not discriminatory; however, systemic and cultural barriers tend to limit the share of women's engagement in the digital system.²³

Conclusion

It cannot be over emphasized that there is a need to end all forms of gender disparity in Nigeria. To achieve a balanced representation of men/women, organizations are to consistently articulate practicable policies so that men/women can play a key role in the economic, political and social areas, for the country to achieve female participation in invention and creation and this inclusivity can thus benefit Nigeria from the intellectual property

perspective. Consequential will give room for economic development, responsive government, healthier children and job creation. Specific attention need to be emphasized to gender in order for Nigeria to achieve gender-positive result in ICT. The need for gender inclusiveness is to understand the difference in the outcome of integrating both men and women in policy design, and project implementation in the process of digitalizing the Nigerian economy. Thus gender issues have been identified, and public opinion should be of concern to Nigeria government and policy makers.

Recommendations

A synergy should be encouraged between all stake-holders that would include gender equality should be encouraged and be sustained as this would advance ICT production in Nigeria. The need to work in coordination, collaboration, and corporation in ICT environment by all actors yield a more inclusive, and democratically gender based information society in Nigeria. There is need for policy makers to identify and address fundamental issues like infrastructure, relevance, accessibility, affordability, and both computer software and hardware as stated in this research which relate to ICT and gender. In summary we recommend an all-inclusive deliberate ICT policy that attract and encourages women participation in ICT developmental framework.

Endnotes

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